

Q1. Please briefly describe the process you followed to design the hierarchical structure for the Study Assignment, and elaborate on how these steps align with the major principles of Object-Oriented Programming.

+3pts for answers that reasonably and correctly discussed some/all of the following principles:

- **Abstraction:**
- To simplify reality and focus only on the properties and external behaviors rather than inner details
- **Encapsulation:**
- Hiding the implementation details (data and the programs that manipulate the data) of an object from the clients of the object
- **Inheritance:**
- A class can derive its methods and properties from another class
- **Polymorphism:**
- Overriding methods among subclasses, and determining which overridden method to execute depending on data types

Q2. Please implement the toString() method in EACH class given the program description in the Study Assignment (directly add to the existing skeleton java programs). Use super() to reduce code redundancy if needed.

Q3. Given the UML diagram, which of the following code snippets is correct? Select ALL that apply.

AC

**+1pt for each
0pts if B/D is also selected**

- A. `Animal a = new Husky();`
`System.out.println(a);`
- B. `Cat c = new Husky();`
`System.out.println(c);`
- C. `Dog d1 = new Dog();`
`d1.bark();`
- D. `Dog d2 = new Husky();`
`d2.howl();`

Q4. Assume the code snippet is error-free, which of the following UML diagrams correctly represents the class structure? Select ALL that apply.

ACD

+1pt for each
0pts if B is also selected

```
Animal a1 = new Husky();
System.out.println(a1);
```

```
Dog d1 = new Dog();
d1.bark();
```

```
Dog d2 = new Husky();
d2.howl();
```

```
Animal a2 = new Cat();
System.out.println(a2);
```


D.